

The lateral area of exponent function

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We view a revolution solid around the x-axis:

The known formula of lateral area can be written:

$$M = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot \int_{x_1}^{x_2} f(x) \cdot \sqrt{1 + f'(x)^2} \, dx$$

We choose the function: $f(x) = b \cdot a^{mx}$ $a, b > 0$ $m \in \mathbb{R}$

The case $m=0$:

It is $f(x)=b$, it follows to the lateral area: $M = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot b \cdot (x_2 - x_1)$

We assume $a, b > 0$, we get for the lateral area:

$$M = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot \int_{x_1}^{x_2} b \cdot a^{mx} \cdot \sqrt{1 + b^2 (\ln a)^2 a^{2mx} \cdot m^2} \, dx$$

with the differentiation: $f'(x) = b \cdot \ln a \cdot a^{mx} \cdot m$

We show the following formula of lateral area:

$$M = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot \left[\frac{b m \ln a a^{mx} \cdot \sqrt{b^2 m^2 (\ln a)^2 a^{2mx} + 1} + \operatorname{arcsinh}(b m \ln a a^{mx})}{2 m^2 (\ln a)^2} \right]_{x_1}^{x_2}$$

$$= 2 \cdot \pi \left[F(x) \right]_{x_1}^{x_2}$$

Proof with differentiation of $F(x)$:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{b a^{mx}}{2 m \ln a} \cdot \sqrt{b^2 m^2 (\ln a)^2 a^{2mx} + 1} \right)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \cdot a^{mx} \cdot b \cdot \sqrt{a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2 + 1} + \frac{\frac{1}{2} \cdot a^{3mx} \cdot (\ln a)^2 \cdot b^3 \cdot m^2}{\sqrt{a^{2mx} \cdot (\ln a)^2 \cdot b^2 \cdot m^2 + 1}}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{1}{2 m^2 (\ln a)^2} \cdot \operatorname{arcsinh}(b \cdot m \cdot \ln a \cdot a^{mx}) \right)$$

$$= \frac{\frac{1}{2} \cdot a^{mx} \cdot b}{\sqrt{a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2 + 1}}$$

We construct the sum of differentiations with the value: $A := a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2 + 1$

$$F'(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{A}} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot a^{mx} \cdot b \cdot A + \frac{1}{2} \cdot a^{3mx} \cdot (\ln a)^2 b^3 m^2 + \frac{1}{2} a^{mx} \cdot b \right)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\sqrt{A}} \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot a^{mx} \cdot b \left(A + a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2 + 1 \right)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\sqrt{A}} \cdot \frac{1}{2} a^{mx} \cdot b \cdot 2A$$

$$= b \cdot a^{mx} \cdot \sqrt{A}$$

The differentiation is equal to the integrand. The proof is done.